

JOHNS HOPKINS

WHITING SCHOOL
of ENGINEERING

A Critical Post Operational Review:
Environmental Impact Assessment for
Jebel Ali Power and Desalination Station M,
Dubai, UAE

Gary D. Moore

Prepared in partial fulfillment of 575.437 Environmental Impact Assessment

December, 2016

Outline

Part One

Comparison of NEPA and UAE EIA Program

Introduction

UAE EIA Framework

Comparative Analysis

Part Two

EIS Critical Review

Background

Purpose and Need for Action

Alternations to the Proposed Action

Affected Environment

Impact Analysis Framework

Impacts of the Alternatives

Cumulative Impact

Other factors Considered

Summary and Evaluation of the EIS

Part 1: Introduction

- The United Arab Emirates (UAE) under Law 24 (1999) has an environmental impact assessment (EIA) program.
- The Environment Agency – Abu Dhabi (EAD) may require an EIA for any development project that has the potential to effect the environment.

Part One: UAE EIA Framework

- The impact assessment framework in the UAE is similar to NEPA, but substantially weaker, lacking requirements in fundamental areas. A comparative analysis of the two programs (next slide) is included.
- The UAE EIA program is a NEPA inspired ‘command and control’ policy administered by the Environment Agency – Abu Dhabi (EAD)
- The UAE EIA process is part of a landuse control and environmental protection process, requiring state review and approval of a proposed landuse project prior to construction.

Part One: Comparative Analysis

- Substantial differences exist between NEPA and the UAE EIA program. The most significant differences are summarized below.
- The UAE EIA process:
 - No public/stakeholders input in the process
 - No public/stakeholder review of EIA
 - Only partial requirements for mitigation measures; they are included in an EIA, but no verification of implementation or effectiveness is required.
 - Projects requiring an EIA are seldom rejected, withdrawn, or scaled back, regardless of the environmental impacts. (Heaton and Burns, Table 2, p. 248, 2014)

Part Two: Background

- In 2009 an environmental impact assessment was performed by Environmental International Consultants for the expansion of an existing electrical power production and desalination plant in the UAE. The EIA report, “ Environmental Impact Assessment for Jebel Ali Power and Desalination Station M” is the subject of this review.
- The goal of submitting the EIA is receiving an approval for the proposed project from the Environment Agency – Abu Dhabi. An approval is formalized by the issuance of an Environmental Permit, which is one of the permits required to construct a project.
- Under the UAE EIA program, neither a Record of Decision nor Alternative Analysis are required
- The project was approved and construction. This presented an opportunity to conduct a limited post-construction and operation audit of information media for published environmental impacts and/or concerns.

Part Two: Purpose and Need for Action

- This is an infrastructure project. It is designed to generate electrical power and produce drinkable water to meet the increasing demands for utility services from a growing industrial sector and residential population.
- This project, i.e., Jebel Ali Power and Desalination Station M, is an expansion of an existing power plant. The existing plant and the expansion (this project, Station 'M') are located on the coast of the Arabian Gulf.

Part Two: Alternatives to the Proposed Action

- Under the UAE EIA program, project alternatives are not assessed. Rather the proposed project is solely the focus of an EIA.
- For this project, the proposed action is: construction and operation of the Jebel Ali Power and Desalination Station M.

Part Two: Affected Environment

The proposed project is to be located:

- coastal area southwest of Doha (the capital city of Qatar)
- In a mixed-use industrial, commercial, and residential area
- marine coastal and near-coastal ecosystem are located to the immediate southwest along a wide intertidal area
- to the northeast are recreational beaches used by residents and tourists

The coastal marine environment includes sensitive and/or protected ecosystems (see Table 1):

Table 1

Shallow bays	Saltmarshes
Coral reefs	Rocky shores
Seaweed meadows	Bird islands
Intertidal flats	Cyanobacteria mats
Mangroves	Coastal sabkhas

Source: EIA, 2009, Environmental International Consultants.

Part Two: Affected Environment

- Environmental conditions potentially negatively (and positive where noted) impacted by the proposed project are presented in Table 2

Table 2

Noise environment	Construction worker health and safety
Air quality – dust and other emissions	Traffic and transportation systems
Both terrestrial and marine flora and fauna near the proposed project	Socioeconomic – employment (positive)

Source: EIA, 2009, Environmental International Consultants.

Part Two: Affected Environment

- The analysis methodologies used in the EIA are not described. However, the following was interpreted from EIA.
- The EIA was based on:
 - a combination of profession judgement (unnamed professionals)
 - limited references to scientific literature
 - references to historical sampling and analysis performed by national and international organizations (baseline conditions)
 - In a rare instance cited in the 2009 EIA report, EIA professionals collected two water samples of the Arabian Gulf.

Part Two: Affected Environment

- The following baseline conditions were described in the EIA:

Climate and Atmosphere

Landuse – undeveloped desert

Air quality

Terrestrial flora and fauna

Marine flora and fauna

Marine ecology

Cultural Heritage

Water quality (including the marine environment)

Landscape and topography

Area recreation

Population

Part Two: Affected Environment

Baseline conditions summary (EIA, 2009, Environmental International Consultants):

The site for the proposed project is a mix of undeveloped desert and existing industrial use (i.e., existing powerplant). The surrounding areas include marine ecosystems and coastal habitats with associated flora and fauna, and recreational beaches; other industrial activities (aluminum smelting plant) southwest of the existing powerplant. Between 3 and 10 kilometers from the proposed project there exists several high density population centers. The closest of these is located 3 kilometers north (Dubai marina and Jumeirah Lake Towers (120,000 population). Other resort and/or residential developments are planned for the area including the construction of two large 'palm islands' along the coast near the proposed project site.

Part Two: Impact Analysis Framework

- A simple matrix method was used to classify the potential severity and likelihood of occurrence of an action to infer an impact (see Tables 5.1 and 5.2 in EIA, 2009).
- No supporting information was provided such as:
 - No - Source of matrix methodology
 - No - Assumptions inherent in the matrix methodology
 - No - Limitations in the matrix methodology
 - No - References from peer-reviewed scientific literature documenting prior successful application of the methodology

Part Two: Impact Analysis Framework

It appears the matrix method is implemented as follows.

1. The potential intensity of an action is classified as: Beneficial, Adverse; Short or Long Term; Localized or Regional.
2. Next, the potential severity of an action is classified as: Slight; Low; Medium; High.
3. Lastly, once the above qualitative classifications are made, the Tables 5.1 and 5.2 (EIA, 2009, pp. 5-2 and 5-3) are used to estimate impact of an action. According to Table 5.2 the possible impact classifications are: Unlikely; Negligible; Minor; Moderate, Major.

- According to Table 5.2, impacts classified as Moderate should be mitigated, and those classified as Major must be mitigated.
- Only potential direct and indirect impacts were assessed; **cumulative impacts were not assessed.**

Part Two: Impact Analysis Framework

Estimates of specific impacts were made as described below:

- Pollution discharges: For all media (soil, water, air) the source(s) of individual potential contaminant concentrations were not provided. It is assumed these concentrations were obtained from the equipment manufacturer's design specifications.
- Resources required or consumed for construction and operation: No consideration of resources required or consumed was included in the EIA.
- Costs: Monetary costs were not part of the EIA. However, the estimated cost of construction of Station M was included under the general project description, as was an estimate of the number of jobs to be created.

Part Two: Impacts of the Alternatives

No project alternatives are included in the EIA.

Part Two: Cumulative Impact

Cumulative impacts are not considered in the EIA.

Part Two: Other Factors Considered

According to the EIA (section 6.1, p. 6-1), " The proposed Power and Desalination Plant 'M' will be constructed and operated according to high environmental, health, and safety (EHS) standards.

However, some mitigation measures (focused on the construction and operation of the expansion) are proposed as described below:

During construction

- **Dust emissions:** roads watered, stockpiles covered, transport dump trucks materials covered
- **Effluent Runoff:** collected and properly disposed offsite
- **Traffic and Transport:** avoid peak hours, notices published for large over-land transport, staggering working hours, construction worker transported to site using bus.
- **Solid Waste:** only licensed contractors will be used, disposal procedures will be audited by the State, strict manifest procedures followed.

Part Two: Other Factors Considered

During Construction (continued)

- **Solid Waste:** On-site engineer assigned to ensure all waste management management procedures are followed
- **Occupational safety and health:** a range of industry standard measures to protect worker health and safety.

During Operation

- **Occupational safety and health:** A full time HSE department
- **Emissions:** high efficiency fuel, low NOx burners, stack design height to ensure atmospheric dilution of discharge
- **Noise:** air compressors equipped with air silencers, outdoor equipment will meet less than 85 dB limit standard
- **Visual Impact:** trees to be strategically planted along the property line to hide plant construction view

Part Two: Other Factors Considered

An extensive environmental monitoring program will be implemented. A summary of the monitoring program is provided below (section 6.4, p. 6-11).

- Ambient air quality in and around the plant
- Stack monitoring to assess the gas emissions
- Marine water quality at intake and at final discharge point
- Ambient noise levels around the plant boundary
- The noise levels of major equipment at distance
- Assessment of quality and quantity of solid waste

No discussion of what would be done to modify operations when a monitored environment indicates degradation.

Trade Offs

It appears, based on the poor quality of the environmental impact information contained in the EIA, the State is willing to trade potential environmental degradation for long term increases in electrical power generation and drinking water production.

Part Two: Other Factors Considered

Irreversible or Irretrievable Resource Commitments:

Based on research of published scientific investigations concerning environmental impacts of desalination plants, and the high concentration of such plants in the Arabian Gulf, marine ecosystems may be at risk of damage either directly from this project, or, cumulatively from the combined effects of the numerous other plants operating or proposed in the region.

This situation may represent a shift causing irreversible damage on the scale of several human generations.

Part Two: Summary and Evaluation of the EIS

EIA report conclusion:

The EIA was prepared to meet the minimum requirements of the State of Qatar for the issuance of an Environmental Permit.

The report contains a description of the project to be built, and limited description of selected impacts from constructing and operating the plant. Baseline information was presented and limited site specific baseline data were included. Based on analysis of possible project impacts and proposed mitigation measures, the proposed project should be approved.

Part Two: Summary and Evaluation of the EIS

EIA critical review comments:

- **It appears the outcome of the EIA was predetermined, namely little to no adverse environmental impact.**
- Major issues and concerns identified in the critical review are:
 - Project alternatives not included
 - Stakeholder and public input not included
 - Limited to no references included
 - EIA Investigators not identified, qualifications not presented
 - Impact analysis methods not sufficiently described or referenced
 - **Cumulative impacts (potentially serious) not included**
 - EIA report frequently not clear due to poor English
 - Segmentation? i.e., this project is Station M, part of a long line of plant expansions since 1976, e.g., prior Stations A, E, G, K, L; Siemens is currently expanding Station M, to be completed in 2018 (News Release, Water Technology Market, 2015).

Part Two: Summary and Evaluation of the EIS

Major issues and concerns (continued)

Cumulative Effects (additional)

According to Latteman and Hopner (2008):

- "The largest number of desalination plants in the world can be found in the Arabian Gulf with a total seawater desalination capacity of approximately 11 million m³/day which means a little less than half of the worldwide daily production."
- "A key concern of desalination plants are the concentrate and chemical discharges to the marine environment, which may may have adverse effects on water and sediment quality, impair marine life and the functioning and intactness of coastal ecosystems."
- And in addition, "...in recent publications special attention is furthermore given to some regional seas with high or increasing desalination activity, such as the Arabian Gulf.."

Part Two: Summary and Evaluation of the EIS

Major issues and concerns (continued)

Cumulative Effects (additional)

Therefore, based on the above observations, a cumulative effect of impacts from this project may be significant and should be thoroughly investigated by a qualified interdisciplinary team.

Part Two: Summary and Evaluation of the EIS

EIA critical review comments (continued)

Post Audit

A review of published news regarding the EIA (six years following project completion). A summary of the news sources reviewed is presented below:

- Online media searched for reports on the operation and/or impact(s) of Station M. No negative reports found.
- Searched the Dubai Electricity and Water Authority website (url = <https://www.dewa.gov.ae/en>) - no post operation information (regarding the EIA or Plant Station 'M') was discovered.
- Searched all regional news sources through Google/News – no post- construction information (regarding the EIA or Plant Station 'M') was discovered.

Bibliography

- Dawoud, M.A., 2012. Environmental impacts of seawater desalination: Arabian Gulf case study. *International Journal of Environment and Sustainability (IJES)*, 1(3).
- Darwish, M.A., Abdulrahim, H.K. and Mohieldeen, Y., 2015. Qatar and GCC water security. *Desalination and Water Treatment*, 55(9), pp.2302-2325.
- Desalination.biz, 2016. Dubai prepares to add desalination capacity to Jebel Ali power station. [online] Available at: < <http://www.desalination.biz/news/0/Dubai-prepares-to-add-desalination-capacity-at-Jebel-Ali-power-station/8515/>>. [Accessed 5 December 2016]
- Eccleston, C. & Doub, J.P. 2012, *Preparing NEPA Environmental Assessments: A User's Guide to Best Professional Practices*, CRC Press.
- Heaton, C. and Burns, S., 2014. An evaluation of environmental impact assessment in Abu Dhabi, United Arab Emirates. *Impact Assessment and Project Appraisal*, 32(3), pp.246-251.
- Lattemann, S. and Höpner, T., 2008. Environmental impact and impact assessment of seawater desalination. *Desalination*, 220(1), pp.1-15.
- Lee, N. & George, C. 2000, "Environmental assessment in developing and transitional countries", *Journal of Environmental Assessment Policy and Management*, vol. 2, no. 2, pp. 275-277.
- Water Technology, 2015. Siemens to expand M-Station power and desalination plant in Dubai. [online] Available at: < <http://www.water-technology.net/news/newssiemens-to-expand-m-station-power-and-desalination-plant-in-dubai-4517932>>. [Accessed on: 5 December 2016]

Conclusion

